

STUDY OF STUDENTS' PERSONAL LIFE DURING LOCKDOWN PERIOD

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Abstract

Pandemic situation due to COVID-19 has impacted every person's life. The researchers here are college teachers and being teachers and mentors are worried about student's progress, personal and academic life and so on. This made them think about the study for understanding students' personal and academic life. In the present study researchers have collected data on personal, academic and professional (if they are working) life of students during lockdown period. For this research survey method was used. Data was collected using google from using <https://forms.gle/mbNFJ7T8Z4Bxwgme7> link. Likert scale was used to collect data on personal, academic life of students. Data received from 282 students of under graduate and Post Graduate level from Pratibha Senior College. Data was analyzed using graphs and percentage. Only personal life related data is considered for this paper and conclusions were drawn on the basis of collected data to find the fact.

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Introduction:

Deadly virus CORONA made us maintain social distancing and through lockdown government compel us to be at home and not to come out unnecessary only for emergency services were allowed. Initially it was enjoyment but due to restrictions on being isolated, insecure always affect our physical and mental health and it also impact our life. We all are facing such situation due to COVID-19 pandemic, it has compel us to be at home isolated, maintain distancing and there is insecurity. This situation has totally changed our life styles and priorities. It has great impact on personal life, professional life and students' academic life as well. It has given rise to distance learning through online platforms, work from home, etc. due to this being at one place has affected physical health as well as personal life style and also academic learning,

achievements and performances. Here in this study there is an attempt to understand students' academic life during lock down.

Objectives:

- To prepare questionnaire on personal life of students during lockdown
- To collect data from students through google form
- To analyze data to understand students' personal life during lockdown

Scope:

- The results of the study will be representative as it is collected from 282 UG and PG level students it will be useful for teacher to understand personal life of students

Limitations:

- The study is limited to the responses received from 282 respondents of questionnaire through google form link <https://forms.gle/mbNFJ7T8Z4Bxwgme7>. Through this form data about personal life, academic life and professional life was collected but for this research only data related to personal life is considered for analysis.

Research Methodology:

- Survey method is used to study academic life of students during lockdown

Sampling method:

- Non-probability purposive sampling method was used because google form was sent to the self-network available for data collection.

Data collection tool:

- For data collection questionnaire in the form of linear scale was used

Data analysis technique:

- Collected data was analyzed using percentage.

Findings:

Question title:

1. It is unbelievable that the whole India is at home. I have never imagined this situation (278 responses)

60 (57.6%) and 37 (13.3%) students agreed that they have never imagined this unbelievable situation. 45 (16.2%) students were neutral and 13 (4.7%) students disagree and 23 (8.3%) were strongly disagree

2. I am facing physical and medical problems due to lockdown (278 responses)

26 (9.4%) students strongly agree and 27 (9.7%) students agreed that they are facing physical and medical problem. 54 (19.4%) students were neutral and 50 (18%) disagreed and 121 (43.5%) students strongly disagreed

3. I have become lazy and lethargic due to lockdown (279 responses)

76 (27.2%) students strongly agree and 48 (17.2%) students agreed that they have become lazy and lethargic due to lockdown. 66 (23.7%) students were neutral and 41 (14.7%) students disagreed and 48 (17.2%) strongly disagreed.

4. Lockdown has affected my eating habits (over eating/ schedule of eating) (279 responses) 73 (26.2%) students strongly agree and 44 (15.8%) students agreed that lockdown has affected their eating habits 68 (24.4%) students were neutral 35 (12.5%) students disagreed and 59 (21.1%) strongly disagreed.

6. Lockdown has affected my sleeping schedule (279 responses) 08 (38.7%) students strongly agree and 36 (12.9%) students agreed that Lockdown has affected their sleeping schedule 53 (19%) students were neutral 31 (11.1%) students disagreed 51 (18.3%) students strongly disagreed

7. Due to lockdown my physical fitness activities have minimized (unable to go for Gym & Sports) (276 responses)

78 (28.3%) students strongly agree and 50 (18.1%) students agreed that Due to lockdown their physical fitness activities have minimized. 57 (20.7%) students were neutral 32 (11.6%) students disagreed 59 (21.4%) students strongly disagreed

8. I feel upset as I could not meet my relatives and friends due to lockdown (279 responses) 33 (47.7%) students strongly agree and 55 (19.7%) students agreed that I feel upset as I could not meet my relatives and friends due to lockdown 37 (13.3%) students were neutral 16 (5.7%) students disagreed 38 (13.6%) students strongly disagreed

9. I feel lonely due to social distancing (279 responses)

78 (28%) students strongly agree and 39 (14%) students agreed that they feel lonely due to social distancing 63 (22.6%) students were neutral 34 (12.2%) students disagreed 65 (23.3%) students strongly disagreed

10. I have plenty of time but I don't feel to utilize it for study (278 responses)

88 (31.7%) students strongly agree and 55 (19.8%) students agreed that they have plenty of time but don't feel to utilize it for study 72 (25.9%) students were neutral 28 (10.1%) students disagreed 35 (12.6%) students strongly disagreed

14. I spend excess time by watching TV programs (278 responses)

55 (19.8%) students strongly agree and 49 (17.6%) students agreed that 85 (30.6%) students were neutral 43 (15.5%) students disagreed 46 (16.5%) students strongly disagreed

15. I spend excess time on social media due to lockdown (277 responses)

74 (26.7%) students strongly agree and 64 (23.1%) students agreed that they spend excess time by watching TV programs. 74 (26.7%) students were neutral 38 (13.7%) students disagreed 27 (9.7%) students strongly disagreed

16. I spend excess time playing games over media phone (275 responses)

60 (21.8%) students strongly agree and 44 (16%) students agreed that 75 (27.3%) students were neutral 42 (15.3%) students disagreed 54 (19.6%) students strongly disagreed

17. I help my parents in household work & other documentation work (278 responses)

41 (50.7%) students strongly agree and 55 (19.8%) students agreed that they spend excess time playing games over media phone. 51 (18.3%) students were neutral 16 (5.8%) students disagreed 15 (5.4%) students strongly disagreed.

18. I have tried to learn different skills during Lockdown period (276 responses)

98 (35.5%) students strongly agree and 65 (23.6%) students agreed that they have tried to learn different skills during Lockdown period 65 (23.6%) students were neutral 26 (9.4%) students disagreed 22 (8%) students strongly disagreed.

19. I have saved money due to lockdown as there is restriction on travelling, shopping and outing (275 responses)

24 (45.1%) students strongly agree and 55 (20%) students agreed that they have saved money due to lockdown as there is restriction on travelling, shopping and outing 47 (17.1%) students were neutral 19 (6.9%) students disagreed 30 (10.9%) students strongly disagreed

20. I am happy that Lockdown has given time to nurture my hobbies. (275 responses)

80 (29.1%) students strongly agree and 43 (15.6%) students agreed that they are happy that Lockdown has given time to nurture their hobbies. 92 (33.5%) students were neutral 31 (11.3%) students disagreed 29 (10.5%) students strongly disagreed

21. Lockdown has increased the conflict among family members as we all are frustrated at home (273 responses)

45 (16.5%) students strongly agree and 43 (15.8%) students agreed that Lockdown has increased the conflict among family members as we all are frustrated at home. 79 (28.9%) students were neutral 33 (12.1%) students disagreed 73 (26.7%) students strongly disagreed

22. Lockdown has increased cohesiveness among the family members as interaction has increased among the members. (272 responses)

79 (29%) students strongly agree and 63 (23.2%) students agreed that Lockdown has increased cohesiveness among the family members as interaction has increased among the members. 83 (30.5%) students were neutral 31 (11.4%) students disagreed 16 (5.9%) students strongly disagreed

23. Lockdown has provided a lesson that minimum things are required for happy living (273 responses)

19 (43.6%) students strongly agree and 70 (25.6%) students agreed that Lockdown has provided a lesson that minimum things are required for happy living 45 (16.5%) students were neutral 24 (8.8%) students disagreed 15 (5.5%) students strongly disagreed

24. Lockdown has compelled me to understand the importance of Ecological Balance (274 responses)

34 (48.9%) students strongly agree and 73 (26.6%) students agreed that Lockdown has compelled me to understand the importance of Ecological Balance 43 (15.7%) 10 (3.6%) students were neutral 10 (3.6%) students disagreed 14 (5.1%) students strongly disagreed.

Conclusions:

The present data received contains responses depicts how students' personal life has affected due to lockdown. Students experiences were mixed sometime they were negative and they had new positive approached developed when they look at the situation positively.

Lockdown has definitely changed lives it has affected physical and mental habits laziness, lethargy, loneliness and conflicts are common bad impact which was found overcome by their positive , optimistic behavior and approach towards situation this has help them in engaging themselves into creative, activities like nurturing hobbies, learning different skills. They have maintained social relations by using excessive social media, entertained themselves using

social media, games, T.V. shows, helping each other in household work and documentation etc. Important lesson students learn during this period that minimum things are required for happy living, understood the importance of Ecological Balance.

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